

Table S1. Linkage map summary information for the TUM RIL population. Tag SNPs indicate the number of SNPs included in the genetic map.

Linkage group	SNP	Tag SNPs	Total distance (cM)	Average distance	
				(cM)	(bp)
Pv01	818	78	181.05	2.35	1473630.56
Pv02	921	89	276.40	3.14	681314.97
Pv03	1171	132	364.60	2.78	1254108.39
Pv04_a	333	34	103.30	3.13	1249188.33
Pv04_b		11	34.51	3.45	189273.10
Pv05_a	653	19	54.77	3.04	182573.44
Pv05_b		45	116.33	2.64	2758521.50
Pv06	789	59	166.23	2.87	664509.10
Pv07	948	125	337.45	2.72	637995.63
Pv08	808	68	234.87	3.51	1795638.51
Pv09	673	52	144.04	2.82	844200.02
Pv10	734	65	166.88	2.61	1844024.80
Pv11	625	65	189.51	2.96	1377207.69
Total	8473	842	2188.89	3.46	1359289.64

Table S2. Results to contingency Chi-square tests between seed coat color phenotype (black vs brown) and the SNPs mapped on chromosome Pv06 in the TUM RIL subpopulation of colored seeds. Significant associations (highlighted in bold) were considered after application of Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = 0.05$; P-value $\leq 5.9384E-05$).

Marker	Distance	Chr	Position	Chi	P-value
S06_2478502	0	Pv06	2478502	12.4377728	0.00042074
S06_2197326	1.89	Pv06	2197326	20.7480048	5.2386E-06
S06_1406198	3.53	Pv06	1406198	22.2222222	2.4285E-06
S06_2005751	5.15	Pv06	2005751	8.83929294	0.00294813
S06_5174714	6.61	Pv06	5174714	17.3713448	3.0743E-05
S06_5985576	8.38	Pv06	5985576	15.277116	9.2834E-05
S06_6560473	10.15	Pv06	6560473	16.1015953	6.0033E-05
S06_4221741	11.97	Pv06	4221741	23.6413043	1.1607E-06
S06_8725847	14.84	Pv06	8725847	19.4628627	1.0257E-05
S06_8345955	16.42	Pv06	8345955	19.5461538	9.8198E-06
S06_9113662	18.51	Pv06	9113662	18.1620238	2.0288E-05
S06_10209448	19.9	Pv06	10209448	18.7541411	1.487E-05
S06_14037821	26.12	Pv06	14037821	16.0205643	6.2658E-05
S06_13376341	28.53	Pv06	13376341	16.0205643	6.2658E-05
S06_15752780	35.02	Pv06	15752780	10.7123203	0.00106424
S06_15606355	37.1	Pv06	15606355	12.5476508	0.0003967
S06_15913470	39.19	Pv06	15913470	8.97971947	0.00272993
S06_16037751	41.58	Pv06	16037751	16.2178163	5.6461E-05
S06_16235966	43.36	Pv06	16235966	14.3123732	0.00015484

Table S3. Results to contingency Chi-square tests between seed coat color phenotype (black vs. brown) and the SNPs mapped on chromosome Pv08 in the TUM RIL subpopulation of colored seeds. Significant associations (highlighted in bold) were considered after application of Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = 0.05$; P-value $\leq 5.9384E-05$).

Marker	Distance	Chr	Position	Chi	P-value
S08_2335059	40.08	Pv08	2335059	15.0097847	0.00010696
S08_3183715	45.13	Pv08	3183715	35.7810665	2.2078E-09
S08_3430092	48.03	Pv08	3430092	32.9153605	9.626E-09
S08_3611625	49.92	Pv08	3611625	24.4875842	7.479E-07
S08_4091418	54.37	Pv08	4091418	21.9256996	2.8341E-06
S08_4492006	57.79	Pv08	4492006	17.3360342	3.1319E-05
S08_4547222	60.57	Pv08	4547222	17.2870753	3.2137E-05
S08_5164857	65.77	Pv08	5164857	15.8060326	7.0178E-05

Table S4. List of annotated genes found for the bounded region in the chromosome Pv07 from the reference genome (available at <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html>).

Gene ID	Gene Define	Start	End
Phvul.007G168900	(1 of 2) PTHR31447:SF2 - OXIDOREDUCTASE, 2OG-FE(II) OXYGENASE FAMILY PROTEIN	28533842	28539284
Phvul.007G169000		28558456	28559106
Phvul.007G169100	(1 of 1) PTHR12183:SF18 - RING-TYPE UBIQUITIN E3 LIGASE	28561095	28565625
Phvul.007G169200		28567724	28572568
Phvul.007G169300	(1 of 12) K10523 - speckle-type POZ protein (SPOP)	28586728	28592046
Phvul.007G169400		28593173	28600002
Phvul.007G169500	(1 of 2) PTHR12550:SF5 - HUA2-LIKE PROTEIN 2-RELATED	28604020	28616394
Phvul.007G169601	(1 of 3) 1.11.1.9 - Glutathione peroxidase	28622158	28625199
Phvul.007G169700	(1 of 2) PTHR33102:SF11 - DVL14-RELATED	28628079	28628216
Phvul.007G169800	(1 of 1) PTHR16223:SF12 - F15K9.11 PROTEIN	28630380	28634856
Phvul.007G169900	(1 of 16) PF11955 - Plant organelle RNA recognition domain (PORR)	28640684	28642738
Phvul.007G170000		28643176	28643586
Phvul.007G170100	(1 of 2) PTHR11088:SF30 - ADENYLATE ISOPENTENYLTRANSFERASE 3, CHLOROPLASTIC	28653126	28654094
Phvul.007G170200	(1 of 158) PF00010 - Helix-loop-helix DNA-binding domain (HLH)	28661034	28663044
Phvul.007G170300	(1 of 1) PTHR32019:SF2 - R3H DOMAIN-CONTAINING PROTEIN 4	28673883	28677831
Phvul.007G170400	(1 of 4) 5.3.3.17 - Trans-2,3-dihydro-3-hydroxyanthranilate isomerase	28681393	28683600
Phvul.007G170600	(1 of 4) 5.3.3.17 - Trans-2,3-dihydro-3-hydroxyanthranilate isomerase	28693349	28695884
Phvul.007G170800	(1 of 4) 5.3.3.17 - Trans-2,3-dihydro-3-hydroxyanthranilate isomerase	28706798	28709356
Phvul.007G170900	(1 of 3) PTHR13683:SF379 - ASPARTYL PROTEASE-LIKE PROTEIN	28710436	28712444
Phvul.007G171000	(1 of 85) PF01657 - Salt stress response/antifungal (Stress-antifung)	28716551	28717193
Phvul.007G171100		28713515	28716101
Phvul.007G171200	(1 of 7) PF13515 - Fusaric acid resistance protein-like (FUSC_2)	28721094	28724624
Phvul.007G171333	(1 of 2) PTHR11514:SF28 - TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR TT8	28752132	28766155
Phvul.007G171466		28772413	28774743
Phvul.007G171600		28775883	28778302
Phvul.007G171700	(1 of 197) PF01535//PF13041 - PPR repeat (PPR) // PPR repeat family (PPR_2)	28781684	28784401
Phvul.007G171800	(1 of 3) K07870 - Ras homolog gene family, member T1 (RHOT1, ARHT1)	28796228	28809176

Phvul.007G171900	(1 of 11) PF11250 - Fantastic Four meristem regulator (FAF)	28852629	28853975
Phvul.007G172000	(1 of 1) PTHR11649:SF36 - FZL	28865447	28872523
Phvul.007G172100	(1 of 1) PTHR10366:SF278 - CHLOROPLAST STEM-LOOP BINDING PROTEIN OF 41 KDA A, CHLOROPLASTIC	28873097	28875434
Phvul.007G172200	(1 of 2) K14319 - Ran GTPase-activating protein 1 (RANGAP1)	28876617	28879430
Phvul.007G172300	(1 of 2) PTHR32241:SF5 - INACTIVE PATATIN-LIKE PROTEIN 9-RELATED	28896346	28898263
Phvul.007G172400	(1 of 1) PTHR20982:SF8 - RIBOSOME-RECYCLING FACTOR, CHLOROPLASTIC	28904987	28909111
Phvul.007G172500	(1 of 2) PTHR34798:SF1 - TIC-LIKE PROTEIN	28921204	28926741
Phvul.007G172600	(1 of 2) K14963 - COMPASS component SWD3 (WDR5, SWD3, CPS30)	28944115	28947838
Phvul.007G172700	(1 of 16) PF05910 - Plant protein of unknown function (DUF868) (DUF868)	28948890	28949792
Phvul.007G172800	(1 of 1) PTHR13087 - NF-KAPPA B ACTIVATING PROTEIN	28967668	28969505

Table S5. List of annotated genes found for the bounded region in the chromosome Pv06 from the reference genome (available at <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html>).

Gene ID	Gene Define	Start	End
Phvul.006G002400	(1 of 1) PTHR10984:SF32 - ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM VESICLE TRANSPORTER PROTEIN	2567269	2578280
Phvul.006G002500	(1 of 4) PTHR23012:SF25 - RING/U-BOX DOMAIN-CONTAINING PROTEIN	2579901	2587229
Phvul.006G002700	(1 of 2) PTHR33179:SF7 - GENOMIC DNA, CHROMOSOME 3, P1 CLONE:MKA23	2616462	2617801
Phvul.006G002800	(1 of 38) PF00076//PF14111 - RNA recognition motif. (a.k.a. RRM, RBD, or RNP domain) (RRM1) // Domain of unknown function (DUF4283) (DUF4283)	2642561	2643752
Phvul.006G002900	(1 of 3) 2.7.7.15 - Choline-phosphate cytidyltransferase/ Phosphorylcholine transferase	2834326	2841110
Phvul.006G003000	(1 of 1) PTHR35491:SF2 - DENTIN SIALOPHOSPHOPROTEIN-RELATED PROTEIN	2912622	2916982
Phvul.006G003100	(1 of 1198) 2.7.11.1 - Non-specific serine/threonine protein kinase/ Threonine-specific protein kinase	2922211	2925808
Phvul.006G003200	(1 of 3) K12394 - AP-1 complex subunit sigma 1/2 (AP1S12)	2929096	2933958
Phvul.006G003300	(1 of 3) PTHR11040:SF35 - ZINC TRANSPORTER 3-RELATED	2981973	2984348
Phvul.006G004580	(1 of 284) PF08263 - Leucine rich repeat N-terminal domain (LRRNT2)	3032481	3033239
Phvul.006G003400	(1 of 95) KOG0472 - Leucine-rich repeat protein	3033325	3035007
Phvul.006G003500	(1 of 2) PTHR33405:SF1 - PROTEIN FLC EXPRESSOR	3122637	3123308
Phvul.006G003600	(1 of 14) KOG4579 - Leucine-rich repeat (LRR) protein associated with apoptosis in muscle tissue	3130231	3131448
Phvul.006G005000		3335928	3350431
Phvul.006G005100	(1 of 3) K16285 - RING/U-box domain-containing protein (XERICO)	3365013	3366591
Phvul.006G005800	(1 of 1) K08775 - breast cancer 2 susceptibility protein (BRCA2, FANCD1)	3414015	3418388
Phvul.006G005700	(1 of 1) PTHR13271:SF44 - RIBULOSE-1,5-BISPHOSPHATE CARBOXYLASE/OXYGENASE SMALL SUBUNIT N-METHYLTRANSFERASE I-RELATED	3719706	3726056
Phvul.006G005500	(1 of 2) PTHR24096:SF219 - LONG CHAIN ACYL-COA SYNTHETASE 8	3750888	3767103
Phvul.006G005600	(1 of 6) PTHR32166:SF33 - HAT FAMILY DIMERIZATION DOMAIN-CONTAINING PROTEIN	3758445	3759115
Phvul.006G005400	(1 of 2) PTHR24096:SF219 - LONG CHAIN ACYL-COA SYNTHETASE 8	3834392	3854595
Phvul.006G005300	(1 of 2) PTHR24012:SF478 - GENOMIC DNA, CHROMOSOME 3, P1 CLONE: MJH23	3864772	3867944
Phvul.006G005200	(1 of 2) PTHR31717:SF8 - ZINC FINGER PROTEIN CONSTANS-LIKE 10-RELATED	3877293	3882710
Phvul.006G020000	(1 of 2) PTHR26374:SF191 - C2H2-TYPE ZINC FINGER FAMILY PROTEIN	4028235	4029638
Phvul.006G019900	(1 of 1198) 2.7.11.1 - Non-specific serine/threonine protein kinase/ Threonine-specific protein kinase	4036094	4050882
Phvul.006G019800	(1 of 2) PTHR11595:SF24 - ELONGATION FACTOR 1-BETA 1-RELATED	4071132	4073164
Phvul.006G019700	(1 of 3) PTHR22763//PTHR22763:SF24 - RING ZINC FINGER PROTEIN // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	4079339	4081845

Phvul.006G019600	(1 of 3) PTHR22763//PTHR22763:SF24 - RING ZINC FINGER PROTEIN // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	4124741	4127305
Phvul.006G019500	(1 of 1) 2.7.1.148 - 4-(cytidine 5'-diphospho)-2-C-methyl-D-erythritol kinase/CMK	4209855	4215227
Phvul.006G019400		4220889	4225901
Phvul.006G019300	(1 of 5) KOG0531 - Protein phosphatase 1, regulatory subunit, and related proteins	4251555	4255792
Phvul.006G019411	(1 of 4) PTHR10857:SF46 - DCD (DEVELOPMENT AND CELL DEATH) DOMAIN PROTEIN	4266650	4267710
Phvul.006G019522	(1 of 4) PTHR10857:SF46 - DCD (DEVELOPMENT AND CELL DEATH) DOMAIN PROTEIN	4267732	4268361
Phvul.006G019000	(1 of 2) PTHR12899:SF5 - RIBOSOMAL L18P/L5E FAMILY PROTEIN	4271214	4276999
Phvul.006G019100		4274458	4275446
Phvul.006G018900	(1 of 2) 5.3.3.2 - Isopentenyl-diphosphate Delta-isomerase / Methylbutenylpyrophosphate isomerase	4289531	4317118
Phvul.006G018800	(1 of 2) K13083 - flavonoid 3',5'-hydroxylase (CYP75A)	4328040	4334826
Phvul.006G018911	(1 of 2) PTHR23155//PTHR23155:SF560 - LEUCINE-RICH REPEAT-CONTAINING PROTEIN // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	4347888	4349636
Phvul.006G019022	(1 of 2) PTHR23155//PTHR23155:SF560 - LEUCINE-RICH REPEAT-CONTAINING PROTEIN // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	4349690	4351601
Phvul.006G018600	(1 of 1) PTHR11413//PTHR11413:SF50 - CYSTATIN FAMILY MEMBER // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	4382742	4385405
Phvul.006G018500	(1 of 5) PTHR32468:SF17 - CATION/H(+) ANTIporter 10-RELATED	4403805	4407407
Phvul.006G018400		4430331	4431271
Phvul.006G018300	(1 of 5) PTHR32468:SF17 - CATION/H(+) ANTIporter 10-RELATED	4442501	4447162
Phvul.006G018200	(1 of 12) PF00646//PF01344 - F-box domain (F-box) // Kelch motif (Kelch1)	4476623	4478137
Phvul.006G018100	(1 of 55) PF03168 - Late embryogenesis abundant protein (LEA2)	4517069	4520052
Phvul.006G018000	(1 of 5) KOG2930 - SCF ubiquitin ligase, Rbx1 component	4546662	4547300

Table S6. List of annotated genes found for the bounded region in the chromosome Pv08 from the reference genome (available at <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html>)

Gene ID	Gene Define	Start	End
Phvul.008G038300	(1 of 3) PTHR10783:SF43 - PHOSPHATE TRANSPORTER PHO1 HOMOLOG 2-RELATED	3180779	3186062
Phvul.008G038400	(1 of 5) PTHR10641:SF526 - TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR MYB113-RELATED	3188683	3190957
Phvul.008G038500	(1 of 5) PTHR10641:SF526 - TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR MYB113-RELATED	3200640	3203064
Phvul.008G038600	(1 of 5) PTHR10641:SF526 - TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR MYB113-RELATED	3220871	3221951
Phvul.008G038700	(1 of 2) PTHR22811//PTHR22811:SF72 - TRANSMEMBRANE EMP24 DOMAIN-CONTAINING PROTEIN // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	3225457	3228904
Phvul.008G038800	(1 of 46) PF01535//PF13041//PF13812 - PPR repeat (PPR) // PPR repeat family (PPR_2) // Pentatricopeptide repeat domain (PPR_3)	3229740	3232257
Phvul.008G038900	(1 of 197) PF01535//PF13041 - PPR repeat (PPR) // PPR repeat family (PPR_2)	3232696	3239388
Phvul.008G039000	(1 of 1) PTHR31321:SF12 - PECTINESTERASE 31	3240363	3244223
Phvul.008G039100	(1 of 4) K08493 - vesicle transport through interaction with t-SNAREs 1 (VTI1)	3244621	3248022
Phvul.008G039200	(1 of 2) PTHR13018//PTHR13018:SF32 - PROBABLE MEMBRANE PROTEIN DUF221-RELATED // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	3248878	3257042
Phvul.008G039300	(1 of 8) PTHR31194//PTHR31194:SF14 - SHN SHINE, DNA BINDING / TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	3258781	3259986
Phvul.008G039400	(1 of 2) PTHR24343//PTHR24343:SF156 - SERINE/THREONINE KINASE // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	3262038	3269020
Phvul.008G039500	(1 of 1) PTHR24343//PTHR24343:SF183 - SERINE/THREONINE KINASE // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	3269974	3274369
Phvul.008G039600	(1 of 3) PTHR31558:SF1 - F7A19.6 PROTEIN-RELATED	3279971	3285925
Phvul.008G039700	(1 of 197) PF01535//PF13041 - PPR repeat (PPR) // PPR repeat family (PPR_2)	3289359	3291459
Phvul.008G039800	(1 of 2) PTHR24056//PTHR24056:SF188 - CELL DIVISION PROTEIN KINASE // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	3293248	3299655
Phvul.008G039900	(1 of 91) PF03106 - WRKY DNA -binding domain (WRKY)	3302082	3306590
Phvul.008G040000	(1 of 2) K07735 - putative transcriptional regulator (algH)	3320127	3321484
Phvul.008G040100	(1 of 2) PTHR12286:SF5 - SACCHAROPINE DEHYDROGENASE-LIKE OXIDOREDUCTASE	3321764	3324352
Phvul.008G040166	(1 of 8) 2.1.1.154 - Isoliquiritigenin 2'-O-methyltransferase/CHMT	3324541	3325219
Phvul.008G040232	(1 of 8) 2.1.1.154 - Isoliquiritigenin 2'-O-methyltransferase/CHMT	3325246	3326756
Phvul.008G040300	(1 of 1) PTHR12029:SF45 - RRNA METHYLASE-LIKE PROTEIN	3326983	3330032
Phvul.008G040400	(1 of 2) PTHR31621:SF11 - GB	3331603	3332241
Phvul.008G040500	(1 of 2) PTHR11654:SF90 - PROTEIN NRT1/ PTR FAMILY 7.2	3334863	3338979
Phvul.008G040600	(1 of 2) PTHR11654:SF90 - PROTEIN NRT1/ PTR FAMILY 7.2	3347581	3352585

Phvul.008G040700	(1 of 4) PTHR22950:SF280 - TRANSMEMBRANE AMINO ACID TRANSPORTER FAMILY PROTEIN	3364766	3366238
Phvul.008G040800	(1 of 1) PTHR23076:SF54 - ATP-DEPENDENT ZINC METALLOPROTEASE FTSH 6, CHLOROPLASTIC	3369192	3372204
Phvul.008G040900	(1 of 4) PTHR22950:SF280 - TRANSMEMBRANE AMINO ACID TRANSPORTER FAMILY PROTEIN	3375313	3385445
Phvul.008G041100	(1 of 1) PTHR19139//PTHR19139:SF142 - AQUAPORIN TRANSPORTER // SUBFAMILY NOT NAMED	3406533	3410521
Phvul.008G041200	(1 of 3) PTHR23201:SF21 - GIBBERELLIN-REGULATED PROTEIN 4	3428791	3430335

Table S7. List of primer-pairs used to resequencing and genotyping analysis of the *Phvul.006G018800* and *Phvul.008G038400* genes in the TU and Musica genotypes.

Gene	Primer Named	Primer Forward 5' → 3'	Primer Named	Primer Reverse 5' → 3'	T _{annealing}
Phvul.006G018800	F1	GGATAAATGGAACCAACTCTTA	R1	ATCTCTGTACCTGTGCATCATA	60
	F2	ATATTTGGAATTTGTTCTGCTC	R2	TTATACTTGCACACCTTGGTAG	60
	F3	TCTCTCATACTACCAAGGTGTG	R3	TTATTTTAACCCCAAAACACAT	60
	F4	AATTACCCAAACATCCTTTTTA	R4	ATCATCTTCGTCAACAACCTAT	60
	F5	AAGGTATACTGAGTCGTCGAG	R5	CAATCAGTTCCTTACCTACAA	60
	F6	CAATACTTCCCTCATCATCATC	R6	GATCGACTCGACTAGACCTAAG	60
	F8	TAAGTATTCAACTCAGATCCA	R8	ATTTATCATCAACAACCATCAA	60
	F9	TTGGAGAAGAGATAAAAGGATG	R9	TCTATGATGCTTGAAGATGTGT	60
	F10	TGAAAAATAAACTCAGTGGAAA	R10	CTAAGGAATGTAAGCAATAGGG	60
	F11	AGTTTAAGCCAGAGAGTTCTT	R11	CTTTCAACTATTTCTTTGCTT	63
	Phvul.008G038400	Fw1	TCCAGAAATTGTTAGATACGTG	R4	GTAAGAGTTTTCTTCTTGTGC
E1_F		AAGTAAGGTGAGTAATGGTGC	E1_R	GCTCTTTGAGGAACGAGGTA	60
E2_F		AGATGCCAGAAGAGTTGTAGAT	E2_R	CTGTTTCCCAAAGTTTATGC	60
E3_F		CCCTGATTGCAGGAAGACT	E3_R	AAGATTTGGCTCCAAGTTTCAG	60
In2_F		GTAAACGATGCTGTAAAGACCAA	In2_R	GACCACCTGCGTTCACAATTA	61
BSC06	BSC06_F	AGTTTAAGCCAGAGAGTTCTT	BSC06_R	CTTTCAACTATTTCTTTGCTT	63
BSC08	BSC08_F	TCCAGAAATTGTTAGATACGTG	BSC08_R	GTAAGAGTTTTCTTCTTGTGC	61

Table S8. Resequencing coverage for the *Phvul.006G018800* and *Phvul.008G038400* genes. The coverage is estimated based on the G19833 reference gene sequence.

Gene regions	Phvul.006G018800					Phvul.008G038400				
	G19833	TU		MUSICA		G19833	TU		MUSICA	
		Length	Coverage	Length	Coverage		Length	Coverage	Length	Coverage
5' UTR	47	47	100%	47	100%	27	109	100%	46	100%
Exon I	348	348	100%	348	100%	121	121	100%	118	100%
Intron I	1833	812	44%	775	42%	143	140	100%	154	100%
Exon II	555	555	100%	555	100%	130	130	100%	74	57%
Intron II	3169	1715	54%	1552	49%	1441	677	43%	-	-
Exon III	255	255	100%	255	100%	379	380	100%	-	-
3' UTR	580	580	100%	252	43%	34	34	100%	-	-
GenomicSequence	6787	4267	63%	3784	56%	2275	1591	71%	392	16%